

The Effectiveness of Monetary Policy Instruments in Creating Real Sector Output Growth in Nigeria

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Abstract

Monetary policy, a crucial instrument for economic stabilisation, comprises measures to control and manage the quantity, accessibility, cost, and movement of credit and money in an economy in order to accomplish certain macroeconomic policy goals. The purpose of this study was to examine the effectiveness of different monetary policy instruments (money supply, interest rates, exchange rate) on real sector output growth in Nigeria during the period under consideration. To this end, the study used annual time series data from the CBN statistical bulletin and the World Development Indicator (WDI) between 1981 and 2023 for its analysis. The paper also uses various econometric techniques: the Autoregression Distribution Lag (ARDL), Unit Root Test, Bound Co-integration Test, and Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test techniques to obtain its results. According to the Unit Root Test results, some of the model's variables are stationary at level and others at first difference. The co-integration test demonstrates the existence of a long-term correlation between real sector output growth and monetary policy variables. While the money supply, exchange rate, and inflation are found to be effective instruments in the long-run having positive effects on real sector output growth, interest rate is found to be effective in the short-run. Given their long run beneficial effects on the economy, it is advised that the government focus more on controlling money supply, inflation and the exchange rate while interest rate should be considered as a short term measure.

Keywords: Economic Growth, Interest Rate, Monetary Policy, Money Supply.

Introduction

One of the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) primary responsibilities over the years has been to develop and implement monetary policies, support monetary stability, and finance the country's financial system in a manner that enhances social welfare (Central Bank Act of 1958). This role depends on the implementation of monetary policy, which is generally aimed at achieving price

stability, rapid economic growth, full employment equilibrium, and a sound external sector balance (Fasanya, Onakoya, & Agboluaje, 2013).

According to Salako (2013), monetary policy is defined as "a policy involving the discretionary management of the money supply by the monetary authorities for the purpose of achieving the stated or desired economic goals." It is the set of policies intended to control the cost, value, and supply of money in an economy in accordance with the volume of economic activity. In order to control the amount of money in the economy, monetary authorities are to implement several measures by altering the money supply and interest rates. Formally articulating how money affects economic aggregates dates back to Adam Smith's time and subsequently by monetary researchers. The role of monetary policy makers is to bring about sustainable economic growth and development for the nations. Macroeconomic goals such as economic growth, price stability, balance of payments equilibrium, job creation, and many more can be used to achieve this.

An important factor in a country's economic growth is the real sector. It includes manufacturing, services, construction, mining, and agriculture. Producing goods and services with the help of labour and capital is the responsibility of the real sector. As the sector with the greatest influence on a nation's economic growth and job creation, the real sector offers numerous benefits to the nation. The economy's real sector produces tangible goods, creates jobs, and generates revenue for investment and consumption, all of which contribute to the expansion of aggregate demand (Adegioriola and Ben-Obi, 2022). An active and productive real sector fosters balance both internally and externally and increases economic linkages.

Over the past decade, Nigeria's economy has witnessed significant interactions between real sector output and monetary policy instruments: interest rate, money supply, exchange rate and even inflation. These variables have impacted the real sector output in different ways, driven by various government policy implementations and external shocks. For example, between 2015 and 2020 during when Nigeria's economy faced challenges due to declining oil prices, leading to reduced real sector output, low government revenues and economic contraction, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) implemented various measures, such as adjusting the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), control the money supply, and manage exchange rate in order to stabilize the economy and increase real sector output and output of goods and services generally (Emiola, Aderinto and Adeagbo; 2025). These efforts of the government together with other physical policies of the government

started yielding results by 2018 when the country's GDP growth rate turned positive, though at a very low rate.

Research works have been ongoing on how monetary policy is transmitted or what monetary policy should target in order to drive an economy. The findings of these research efforts have helped to model the operating frameworks and refine the policy's tools. Some of the results of these studies favour directing monetary policy variables to the aggregate output level while some favour directing the variables to a disaggregated sectoral output. The responses of the disaggregated components depend heavily on the actual economy's manufacturing, agricultural, and service subsectors. According to Hammed (2020), a disaggregation of the entire economy into distinct sectors is required because different sectors have varied capital intensities, which result in diverse reactions in sectoral productivity to monetary policy change. The disaggregated technique is more useful than the aggregate way for analysing the transmission mechanism of monetary policy since these disparities in responses are largely obscured at the aggregate level (Mishkin, 1996). According to a number of academics, monetary policy initiatives aimed at reviving the agricultural sector ought to concentrate more on the application of differential interest rates, among other things (Osakwe, Ibenta, and Ezeabasili, 2019; Uju and Ugochukwu, 2021). Furthermore, the monetary authority receives crucial information from the magnitude, timing, and persistence of money policy shocks on economic activity, which it uses to formulate policy initiatives aimed at stabilising the macroeconomy in general and the real sector in particular. This has made it necessary to use treasury bills and the money supply as short-term policy tools to preserve macroeconomic stability in Nigeria, especially in the manufacturing sector (Anowor & Okorie, 2016). Examining how monetary policy tools affect Nigeria's real sector production growth and the effectiveness of these policy instruments form the primary goals of this study.

Theoretical review

The foundations of growth and monetary theories form the basis of this investigation. These three schools of thought are Keynesian, Monetarist, and Neoclassical. It has been demonstrated that a wide range of academics hold varying views regarding the function and dimensions of money in achieving macroeconomic goals. As a result, some research attempts to determine the influence or connection between monetary policy and other economic aggregates, including inflation and

output. In addition to other relevant material, it is vital to examine the various schools of thought and their perspectives on the role of money in achieving policy aims and goals.

The Classical and Neo classical monetary theory

The classical theory looked at financial decision-making, saving, and investing. Udule (2014) asserts that "supply creates its own demand" in the classical model of Say's law markets. By focussing on price levels and ways to control inflation, classical economists hold that the economy naturally evolves towards full employment. Utilising the quantity theory and the level of commodity production as the determinant of the general price level, they introduced money. It shows how money affect the economy which may be considered in terms of the equation of exchange:

$$MV = PT$$

The price level was explained using the two comparable formulations of quantity theory, viz. According to the transaction theorist, if the money supply is raised in proportion to the demand for money (T), the price level will likewise rise equip-proportionately, and vice versa. The demand for nominal money balances, according to Cambridge economists, will be proportionate to the level of individual income and, consequently, to the overall income in the economy. The Cambridge equation, which states that $M = KY = KPY$ ($K = 1/v$), where M is the money stock or quantity of money, P is the general level price level, Y is the total money income, and K is the percentage of income (Y) that the people wish to hold as money (called Cambridge K), or the reciprocal of fisher V, where $K = 1/V$ and V is the velocity of money, thus gives the aggregate demand for money.

The Cambridge version highlighted the relationship between the amount of money and GNP. In the old quantity theory, the reciprocal of V is equal to "K," which is another volitional element added to the equation. The impact of doubling the money supply on the GNP, however, will be less than double if K is not equal to 1. Because "K" will be smaller than one, an increase in the money supply will not result in a one-to-one rise in prices. As a result, the proportionality concepts of the quantity theories are rendered meaningless since an increase in the money supply will not be fully transferred into the economy to influence prices and other GNP components.

Keynesian Theory

John Maynard Keynes rejected the classical perspective and created a theory of money demand that placed a strong emphasis on interest rates. The Keynesians model, which modifies the traditional quantity theory of money, makes the assumption that the money supply indirectly affects real GDP through its interest rate transmission mechanism. The foundation of the Keynesian model is the idea of price rigidity and the potential for an economy to function below full employment in terms of output, income, and employment. Thus, expansionary monetary policy may have long-term benefits, in contrast to the view held by traditional economics that an increase in the money supply will only lead to higher inflation. The mechanism of the Keynesian model, according to Udude (2014), modifies the interest rate, which influences investment decisions and, consequently, production and income through the multiplier effect. Say's law and the idea that the economy self-regulates are thus rejected by Keynesian theory.

Empirical Literature

The impact of monetary policy on the real economy in both developed and developing nations has been the subject of numerous studies in the body of existing literature. The knowledge that monetary policy and other macroeconomic factors actually affect the economy differently has been made possible by these studies.

Using the Error Correction Model (ECM), Fasanya, Onakoya, and Agboluaje (2013) investigated how monetary policy affected economic growth in Nigeria between 1975 and 2010. They revealed that a long-run relationship exists among the variables (external reserve, money supply, interest rate, exchange rate and inflation rate) and economic growth. Furthermore, they concluded that money supply and interest rate were found to be insignificant.

Chipote and Makhetha-Kosi (2014) looked at how monetary policy influenced economic growth in South Africa between 2000 and 2010. To check for stationarity in the time series, the study used the Phillips Perron unit root and Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) approaches. The Johansen cointegration and the Error Correction Mechanism are used to differentiate between the variables' long-term and short-term dynamics. The study shows that there is a long-term correlation between the elements. Additionally, the study's main conclusion is that while inflation is a major monetary

policy tool that propels growth in South Africa, the money supply, repo rate, and exchange rate are negligible.

In 2015, Adigwe, Echekeba, and Onyeagba investigated the impact of monetary policy on the Nigerian economy. In order to do this, the Ordinary Least Square Method (OLS) is used to analyse data from 1980 to 2010. The results of the analysis show that monetary policy, as measured by the money supply, has a positive effect on GDP growth but a negative influence on inflation.

In a similar vein, Alavinasab (2016) used an error correction approach to examine how monetary policy affected Iran's economic growth from 1971 to 2011. The findings showed a significant long-term association between inflation, the money supply, and the exchange rate and economic growth.

Anowor and Okorie (2016) examined the impact of monetary policy on economic growth in Nigeria using time-series data from 1982 to 2013. The findings indicate that a higher cash reserve ratio contributed to Nigeria's economic growth.

Onakoya, Ogundajo, and Babatunde (2017) examined the monetary policy stance's capacity to maintain the sustainability of the manufacturing sector. The study analysed time series data from 1981 to 2015 using the Vector Error Correction model and Johansen co-integration. The findings verified that there was a long-term correlation between the variables. The performance of Nigeria's manufacturing sector was found to be positively correlated with monetary policy at the 5% level of statistical significance. There was no discernible short-run correlation between inflation rates and external reserves. The study concludes that monetary policy has a major influence on Nigeria's industrial production.

Ajibola and Adeyemi (2018) investigated how monetary policy affected Nigeria's economic growth. Using the unit root test, co-integration methodology, Granger causality test, and error correction method, with the time series data spans the years 1981–2016. With the exception of interest rate, all estimation variables were stationary at first difference, demonstrating that the model interpretation was not spurious and accurately reflected the relationship between the explanatory factors. However, ECM demonstrates that the exchange rate and money supply have a favourable but insignificant effect. A long-term correlation between monetary policy and economic growth was demonstrated via the Engle-Granger co-integration test. Lastly, the Granger causality technique showed that there is a unidirectional causal relationship between the money

supply and economic growth, a bidirectional causal relationship between interest and economic growth, and a granger causal relationship between economic growth, liquidity ratio and exchange rates.

Osakwe, Ibenta, and Ezeabasili (2019) examined how Nigeria's manufacturing sector performed in relation to monetary policy. The manufacturing sector's output is the dependent variable, and the money supply, cash reserve requirement, monetary policy rate and treasury bill rate are the independent variables. The model was estimated using the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL). The findings show that monetary policy tools only have a short-term, meaningful impact on Nigeria's manufacturing sector production. The study came to the conclusion that monetary policy tools might be more effective in the short run than in the long run for increasing the production of Nigeria's manufacturing sector.

Hammed (2020) investigated the impact of monetary policy shocks on Nigerian industrial production using time series data from 1981 to 2018. The co-integration test was used to determine the long-run associations between the variables, and a structural vector auto-regressive framework was used to examine the presence of shocks. A shock to the interest rate was found to have a negative and negligible impact, whereas a shock to the broad money supply was found to have a big and positive impact. The results of this analysis indicate that a shock to broad money is the primary monetary policy tool that can enhance Nigeria's industrial production. The research work recommended that the government and policymakers should prioritise this variable while implementing unexpected monetary policy.

The impact of monetary policy on Nigeria's industrial growth from 1986 to 2019 was studied by Uju and Ugochukwu (2021). Data for the study were collected using the 2019 issue of the CBN Statistical Bulletin. Using a multiple regression model, the data was estimated using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression approach. The results showed that the Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR) significantly and positively affects the manufacturing sector's gross domestic product in Nigeria. The GDP of the Nigerian manufacturing sector was positively and significantly impacted by Open Market Operation (OMO), as indicated by the Treasury bill rate, whereas the GDP of the Nigerian manufacturing sector was negatively and significantly impacted by the monetary policy rate. The results of the study show that Nigeria's monetary policy is a useful tool for encouraging the growth of the industrial sector.

In a different development, Adegioriola and Ben-Obi (2022) investigated the relationship between the Nigerian economy's real sector and monetary policy tools. The lag model utilised was the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model. According to the results, agricultural production in the present period increases in response to increases in the previous period's exchange rate, inflation rate, service output, and agricultural output. Because of greater interest rates and manufacturing output in the past, agriculture yields less in the current period. Service output from the current period increases if manufacturing, service, and agriculture production increase from the past period. Manufacturing output rises in the present period if the preceding period's manufacturing, agricultural, inflation, money supply, and exchange rates all increased.

In summary, the overall findings of the work reviewed so far indicate that there is somehow a general consensus that there is a direct relationship between monetary policy and economic growth exists.

Methodology and Data

This study follows the Neoclassical framework approach and adopted the methodology of Adegbite, and Alabi (2013) but with little modifications considered appropriate for studying the relationship between monetary policy and real sector output growth in Nigeria, owing to incessant policy shifts experienced in the economy. Thus the model is specified as follows:

$$RSEC = f (MS, INTR, EXTR, INFL) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where:

RSEC = Real Sector Output Growth

MS = Money Supply expressed as a percentage of GDP

INTR = Interest Rate

EXTR = Exchange Rate

INFL = Inflation Rate

Writing this in econometric form and introducing white noise disturbance term, equation (1) can be specified as:

$$RSEC = \beta_0 + \beta_1MS + \beta_2INTR + \beta_3EXCHR + \beta_4INFL + \mu \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where μ is error term capturing the influence of unidentified variables.

β_0 is intercept, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ are the coefficient of the independent variables.

Measurement of Variables and Data Source

This study's primary objective is to investigate the effectiveness with which Nigeria's real sector growth was influenced by monetary policy instruments between 1981 and 2023. The World Development Indicator (WDI,2024) and the CBN Statistical Bulletin (2024) provided the data for the study.

Empirical Results

Unit Roots Test

Examining the unit root property and the data integration order is essential in any time series data. The stationarity property of the variables is confirmed in this study using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root tests. The outcomes of the unit root tests are shown in Table 1.2. The table shows that money supply, interest rate, and exchange rate are only stationary in their first differences, while real sector output growth and inflation remain stationary at level.

Table 1.2 Result of Unit Root Test Using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF)

Variables	At Level			First Difference			Remark
	t-stat	Prob	5%	Prob	5%		
RSEC	-4.4610**	0.0053	-3.5298	-8.7101	0.0000	-3.5331	I(0)
MS	2.4313	1.0000	-3.5266	-6.1582*	0.0000	-3.5298	I(1)
INTR	-3.3383	0.0747	-3.5266	-8.7476*	0.0000	-3.5298	I(1)
INFL	-4.1022**	0.0131	-3.5298	-6.4462	0.0000	-3.5331	I(0)
EXCHR	0.0685	0.9958	-3.5266	-4.7766*	0.0023	-3.5298	I(1)

**, * Significant at level and at first difference at 5% level
Source: Authors Computation, (2025).

Before moving on to additional tests of the variables' statistical characteristics, the ideal lag length for the model was established. Table 1.3 displays the outcome of the selection criterion. With the exception of Final Prediction Error (FPE) and Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), which indicate that lag 3 is ideal, other criteria's results yield a consensus conclusion that lag 2 is optimal based on the sequential modified LR test, Schwarz Information Criterion (SC), and Hannan-Quinn

Information Criterion (HQ). Therefore, the study used lag 3 to increase the degree of freedom in the analysis.

Table 1.3: Lag Length Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-982.8011	NA	1.06e+17	53.39466	53.61235	53.47140
1	-833.3808	36.84913	1.31e+14	46.60331	48.99792	47.44752
2	-807.1613	250.3800*	1.29e+14	46.66923	47.97538*	47.12971*
3	-777.7621	33.37200	1.28e+14*	46.36552*	49.84859	47.59346

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion. LR: sequential modified LR test statistic . FPE: Final prediction error (each test at 5% level). AIC: Akaike information criterion. SC: Schwarz information criterion. HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion. Source: Authors Computation, (2025).

Bound Cointegration Test Result

Once the stationarity problem has been resolved, the study moves on to the cointegration test to determine whether the variables under investigation have a long-term relationship. The outcomes of the ARDL bound approach to co-integration are shown in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4: Result of Cointegration Test

Test Statistic	Value	Df	Prob
F-statistic	8.420980	(5, 24)	0.0001
Chi-square	42.10490	5	0.0000

Authors Computation, (2025).

Source:

According to the bound test results, the F-statistic tabulated value is 8.42, this is higher than the 95% critical Upper Bound Perasan (intercept and trend) value of 4.57 and lower bound value of 3.47. The results of the test show that the variables have a long-term equilibrium relationship.

Long Run ARDL Regression Results

The study then estimates the variables' long- and short-term regression parameters after establishing the long run relationship between them. The outcomes of the anticipated long-run real sector growth equation are shown in Table 1.5.

Table 1.5: Long-run Regression ARDL Results

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Dependent Variable: RSEC</i>			
	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t-statistics</i>	<i>Prob.</i>
C	7.294966	13.99000	0.521441	0.6068
MS(-1)	0.031236*	0.015663	1.994285	0.0488
INTR(-1)	1.714122	0.865806	1.979799	0.0593
INFL(-1)	0.917486*	0.259428	3.536575	0.0017
EXCHR(-1)	0.232065*	0.105425	2.201235	0.0376
R-squared	0.711976	D-W	2.106229	
F. Stat.	4.943864	F.Prob	0.000434	

Source : Authors' computation, 2025: * denotes that the variable is significant at 5% level.

Table 1.5 demonstrates that the money supply is positively signed and significant at 5%, indicating that it eventually promotes increase in real sector output. The result is in line with the a priori prediction. According to the findings, real sector output growth is increased by 0.03% for every 1% increase in the money supply ratio GDP. This demonstrates that one of the key factors influencing Nigeria's real sector output growth is the money supply.

Additionally, the inflation rate is positively signed and significant at the 5% critical level, indicating that it also promotes the growth of the real sector. It satisfies the a priori expectation. According to the findings, real sector output growth is increased by 0.92% for every 1% increase in inflation rate. This demonstrates that inflation also has a significant role in determining the growth of Nigeria's real sector production.

In the same vein, the exchange rate is positively signed and significant at the 5% critical level, indicating that it promotes long-term growth in the Nigeria's real sector. It complies with the a priori prediction since rising exchange rates raise import costs, which promotes local production

and consumption. According to the findings, a 1% increase in the exchange rate will result in a 0.23% increase in real sector output growth. This demonstrates that another key factor influencing Nigeria's real sector output growth is the exchange rate. However, the coefficients of interest rate is not significant at 5%.

It can be concluded at this point that in the long run analysis only money supply, exchange rate and inflation rate are effective instruments of monetary policy that are effective in their effects on real sector output growth in Nigeria.

Short Run Relationship

For the dynamic equilibrium between the short run and the long run relationship, the error correction model (ECM) is estimated and the result is presented in the following table 1.6.

Table 1.6: Short-run Regression Results

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Dependent Variable: DRSEC</i>			
	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>t-statistics</i>	<i>Prob.</i>
@TREND	-1.185328	0.705205	-1.680828	0.1058
D(RSEC2(-1))	0.322701	0.204262	1.579838	0.1272
D(RSEC2(-2))	0.159989	0.171053	0.935316	0.3589
D(MS(-1))	0.001246	0.003067	0.406410	0.6880
D(INTR(-1))	-2.184118	0.850996	-2.566542	0.0169
D(INFL(-2))	-0.291252	0.210658	-1.382581	0.1795
D(EXCHR(-2))	-0.127156	0.164500	-0.772988	0.4471
ECM (-1)	-1.666079	0.277394	-6.006191	0.0000

Source: Authors' computation, 2025: * denotes that the variable is significant at 5% level.

The rate of adjustment from disequilibrium to equilibrium in the subsequent year is indicated by the Error Correction Term (ECT). As expected, the model's ECT sign is negative and statistically significant. This result has an economic implication in that it shows a high rate of adjustment between the real sector output growth and its regressands, with the whole discrepancy between the long-term and short-term dynamics being adjusted within the following year. Only the interest rate is determined to be significant and negative, according to the short-run model's results. Real sector output growth in this case is found to be inversely correlated with interest rates. The result however

conforms to the a priori expectation. The result shows that higher interest rate discourages investment and production in the real sector of Nigerian economy in the short run.

It should be noted that unlike what transpired in the long run estimation, only interest rate is effective in bringing about a change in the real sector output growth in Nigeria. In the short run analysis, money supply, exchange rate and inflation rate are not significant and are not effective instruments in bringing about a desired change in Nigeria's real sector output growth in the short run.

Diagnostic Tests

To verify the model's stability and goodness of fit, diagnostic tests are carried out. These tests include the tests for stability, heteroscedasticity, serial correlation, and normalcy. Table 1.7 presents the findings. From the table, diagnostic tests suggest that the analysis results are free from serial correlation with F stat of 0.8944, a probability value of 0.4232 in the model,

Table 1.7: Diagnostic Tests

Variable	<i>F – value</i>	<i>Prob.</i>
Serial Correlation LM Test	0.8944	0.4232
Normality (Jarque-Bera Stat)	3.6359	0.1624
Heteroscedasticity	0.6682	0.7640

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025.

the residuals are normally distributed with Jacque-Bera statistic of 3.6359 (probability value of 0.1624). With Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey F-statistics of 0.6682 (a probability value of 0.7640), the results are also determined to be heteroscedastic free. When the CUSUM and square of CUSUM tests are used to assess the stability of the model, it is evident from their diagrams in Figure 1 that the plot of CUSUM and square of CUSUM fall within the critical bound of 5% in each instance, confirming both the stability of the model's coefficients and the long-term relationship between the variables.

Figure 1: Cusum and Cusum of Squares

Conclusions

This study looks at how Nigeria's real sector output growth was affected by monetary policy instruments and the effectiveness of these monetary policy instruments from 1981 to 2023. The paper uses the autoregression distributed lag (ARDL), bound co-integration test, and Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test to perform empirical analysis. After confirming the variables' stationarity property and determining that they are $1(0)$ and $1(1)$ processes, ARDL regression estimation shows that, in the long term, the money supply, inflation rate, and exchange rate are significantly effective in boosting real sector output growth in Nigeria, whereas interest rates only is only effective in the short-run.

Recommendations

Interest rates should be carefully controlled in the short run in light of the study's finding in order to create a market-based interest rate that will encourage more investment and production in manufacturing and agriculture, which will raise output in the real sector in the short run. In order to create long run jobs, encourage non-oil exports, and revitalise industries that are currently functioning well below installed capacity, monetary policies should be employed to control inflation and establish an exchange rate that attracts both foreign and domestic investments in the long run.

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